

**THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES: ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE JALINGA INTERACTIVE PLATFORM
IN TEACHING KOREAN.**

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Abstract. *This paper examines the impact of the Jalinga Interactive Platform on language learning outcomes, student engagement, and overall learning experience. It also explores how the platform addresses common challenges in language learning, such as motivation, retention, and practice. Use of innovative technologies in teaching foreign languages has become increasingly important in the digital age. This paper explores the role of innovative technologies in teaching foreign languages, focusing on the example of the Jalinga Interactive Platform in teaching Korean. The Jalinga Interactive Platform is a cutting-edge language learning tool that leverages technology to enhance the language learning experience.*

Keywords: *Jalinga, interactive teaching, platform, Korean language, electron sources.*

Аннотация. *В этой статье рассматривается влияние интерактивной платформы Jalinga на результаты изучения языка, вовлеченность учащихся и общий опыт обучения. Также исследуется, как платформа решает общие проблемы в изучении языка, такие как мотивация, удержание и практика. Использование инновационных технологий в преподавании иностранных языков приобретает все большее значение в эпоху цифровых технологий. В данной статье исследуется роль инновационных технологий в преподавании иностранных языков на примере интерактивной платформы Jalinga в преподавании корейского языка. Интерактивная платформа Jalinga — это передовое средство изучения языка, которое использует технологии для улучшения процесса изучения языка.*

Ключевые слова: *Jalinga, интерактивное обучение, платформа, корейский язык, электронные ресурсы.*

In order to better grasp the content of Korean language courses and improve the level of Korean language teaching for students, colleges and universities must strengthen in the Korean course created for the essence of Korean connotation and teaching analysis, understand the characteristics of Korean language curriculum, and use it to strengthen students understanding of the teaching context so as to realize the optimization of teaching resource allocation. Learning a language other than mother tongue means that we seek to understand others, as expressed by Reagan, Timothy and Osborn (2002) that:

“In studying languages other than our own, we are seeking to understand (and, indeed, in at least a weak sense, to become) the Other – we are, in short, attempting to enter into realities that have, to some degree, been constructed by others and which many of the fundamental assumptions about the nature of knowledge and society may be different from our own. We are, in fact creating new selves in an important sense.” [1]

With regard to language learning, Kumaradevelu (2006) [2] explains that there are classroom procedures that teachers need to apply, modifying the material and facilitating student interaction activities. Modifying this material relates to how the teacher presents the material so that it can be accepted well by the students, while facilitating student interaction activities related to the activities of teachers in assigning tasks to students so that interaction runs smoothly between

students in the classroom. The success of these activities will be greatly influenced by what strategies that teachers use in the learning process.

Every student has his/her own learning style, linguistic knowledge background, and individual pace in teaching and improving. Therefore, most foreign language classes involve students with mixed abilities (Richard, 1998).[3]

Break the limitations of the traditional teaching mode, adopt diversified teaching methods, and create a good environment for students based on the teaching characteristics of Korean language course so as to improve the teaching efficiency. Developers create educational content in *Jalinga* studio. The teacher can use a glass board and a special digital marker for notes that will be shown in the frame. Teacher can bring a presentation and scroll through it in a frame with comments and recommend preparing a presentation for each fifteen-minute block. At the beginning of each presentation, it is necessary to indicate what will be told in the lecture, what main goals and objectives are presented to the audience. Then comes the main part - the presentation of the material, and at the end the results are summed up, the key conclusions are formulated. Based on such a presentation, it is quite easy for the teacher to narrate. In my experience our university teachers make an online content for distance learning and promote Korean language classes with modern strategies. We were lunching several video products in the topic of Geography [4] and History of Korea.[5]

Using methods of Jalinga

Presentations can be shown in several formats. For examples, a standard presentation to the right or left of the lecturer, which lecturer can scroll through? It occupies two-thirds of the screen, the lecturer - one-third. It looks good and readable both on the computer screen and on the phone screen.

In addition to a static presentation with pictures, there are several additional functions, for example, to open a website: certain slides with links to pages of Internet resources are added to the presentation. Lecturer can scroll through them in real time, open different sections. It is possible to build a 3D model that can be rotated by explaining. It is possible to move some elements on the board, for example, puzzle pieces. The functionality of the board in the *Jalinga* studio can be found on YouTube.

There are many contents involved in Korean course teaching, and the teaching forms are diversified. In addition to being able to master the corresponding Korean vocabulary, but also good Korean expression skills, an understanding of the linguistic background and culture of the Korean language, and knowledge of the components of the Korean language elements and requirements. The large amount of scattered knowledge and content learning will inevitably lead to excessive psychological and classwork burdens for students, as well as the need for teachers to teach the Undergo greater pressure.[6]

As I mentioned about *Jalinga* interactive studio which influences to education and new format of teaching Korean language to high mixed ability students changes a lot during the learning via online and improve self-studying, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Jalinga

While teaching Korean in Uzbekistan, I often heard these words while meeting new students at a school event introducing the school to new students. In proportion to the increasing popularity of Hallyu, the enthusiasm of students to learn Korean is also increasing. Technology is also growing rapidly. By the way, the benefits of learning Korean for students through various online methods are currently increasing. One of the useful features of e-learning platforms and smartphone applications is their ability to share texts and multimedia between users.

In summary, the Korean language has become a popular second foreign language in Uzbekistan, but from the point of view of the Korean language teaching situation, it is still existing many deficiencies. These include outdated teaching methods, single subject and content. These problems make it difficult to carry out Korean language teaching activities effectively. Therefore, we also need to investigate the corresponding solutions to these problems and improve classroom teaching efficiency and meet students learning requirements through the application of diversified teaching methods. Based on the findings, factors mostly influencing the difference in the students' achievement are maturity, mother tongue, interest and motivation.

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